

STUDIES ON THE METAL COMPLEXES OF HYDROXAMIC ACIDS.
PART II. COLOURED COMPLEXES OF IRON, VANADIUM AND
MOLYBDENUM WITH NICOTINOHYDROXAMIC ACID
AND THEIR ANALYTICAL USES

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Traces of iron (whether present initially as ferrous or ferric) has been determined spectrophotometrically by measuring the optical density of the golden yellow colour formed between the metal and nicotino-hydroxamic acid at p_H 4.5 to 6.0 at 440 $m\mu$ (Sandell sensitivity 0.014 γ). The empirical compositions of the violet, red and the golden yellow coloured complexes of ferric iron have been determined by Job's method of continued variation, giving metal-ligand ratio of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 respectively.

Vanadium has been determined by measuring the optical density of the golden yellow complex formed between the metal and the reagent in 50% ethanol over the p_H range 2.5 to 4.5 at 440 $m\mu$ (Sandell sensitivity 0.014 γ). A solvent extraction procedure for its determination has also been described. The empirical compositions of a variety of coloured products formed between the metal and the reagent in aqueous and also in 50% ethanol medium have been determined (Job's method). The metal-ligand ratio for all is given by 1:3.

Molybdenum has been estimated by measuring the intensity of its yellow coloured complex with the reagent at 380 $m\mu$ or at 390 $m\mu$ over the p_H range 6.5 to 8.0. The composition of the complex has also been determined (Job's method). It gives a metal-ligand ratio of 1:2.

In a previous communication (Dutta, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 311), the nature and the analytical aspects of the colour reaction of traces of manganese with nicotino- and isonicotino-hydroxamic acids in ammoniacal medium have been fully discussed. In this paper, the results of similar studies on the coloured complexes of iron, vanadium and molybdenum with nicotino-hydroxamic acid have been recorded. The reagent also develops a yellow colour with titanium and uranium under suitable p_H , but the colours are not very sensitive.

Ferric iron develops with excess reagent a violet colour (absorption maximum 500 $m\mu$) at p_H 1.5 to 2.5, a red colour (absorption maximum 460/470 $m\mu$) at p_H 2.8 to 3.0 and a golden yellow colour (absorption maximum 440 $m\mu$) at p_H 4.5 to 6. The last reaction is sensitive, and suitable for the colorimetric estimation of iron (Sandell sensitivity 0.014 γ). (Vanadium interferes seriously). Job's method indicates an 1:1 complex for the violet colour, an 1:2 complex for the red colour and an 1:3 complex for the golden yellow colour.

Ferrous iron develops an intense golden yellow colour with excess reagent above p_H 4.0. The absorption spectrum over the p_H range 4.6 to 6 is perfectly superimposable on that given by an equal amount of ferric iron with the reagent at the same p_H . This colour can be utilised for the colorimetric estimation of iron (Sandell sensitivity 0.014 γ). Ferrous iron does not give rise to the violet colour at lower p_H , characteristic of ferric iron, even on standing for hours. But, when the golden yellow

coloured complex, which is formed by the addition of ferrous iron to the reagent in near neutral or alkaline range, is brought to p_H 1.5 to 2 or to about 3, the same violet or red colour, characteristic of ferric iron, is developed. Das Gupta and Dhar (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, **11B**, 500, 520) report that oxalohydroxamic acid exhibits only a weak colour reaction with ferrous iron, whereas that with benzohydroxamic acid (Das Gupta and Singh, *ibid.*, 1952, **11B**, 268) is quite strong. Salicylhydroxamic acid also develops an intense red to golden yellow colour with ferrous iron in alkaline medium. These facts probably suggest that in the near neutral to alkaline range, ferrous iron is oxidised to the ferric state almost instantaneously, whereas in strong acid solution, this oxidation of the complex does not occur to an appreciable extent. Job's method of continued variation between ferrous iron and the reagent at p_H 5.3 shows an 1:3 complex. Nicotinohydroxamic acid therefore appears to be a suitable colorimetric reagent for iron irrespective of the initial oxidation state of the metal.

Vanadium (added as vanadate) develops with the reagent a series of colours. In aqueous medium, a dull purple colour (absorption maximum $500 m\mu$) at a p_H of about 3, and a bright purple colour (absorption maximum $500-510 m\mu$) at a p_H of about 8 are formed. Neither of these two colours offers a suitable p_H range for colorimetric determination of vanadium, nor are they sensitive. On the other hand, in 50% alcoholic medium, there appears an intense golden yellow colour (absorption maximum $440 m\mu$) in acid medium and in alkaline medium, a bright purple colour (absorption maximum $500-510 m\mu$). The golden yellow colour is suitable for colorimetric estimation of traces of vanadium over the p_H range 2.5 to 4.5. The method is highly sensitive (Sandell sensitivity 0.014γ). The dull purple colour formed in aqueous medium (p_H 3.1) can be extracted with *isoamyl* or *isobutyl* alcohol. The absorption spectrum of the extracted colour is similar to that of vanadium complex in 50% ethanol (absorption maximum $440 m\mu$, sensitivity 0.012γ). Iron interferes seriously during the estimation of vanadium in 50% alcohol. However, in presence of uranium and molybdenum, vanadium can be estimated by extraction of the dull purple colour in aqueous medium with *isobutyl* or *isoamyl* alcohol. But iron interferes even by this procedure. These colour reactions are not shown by vanadium in presence of a large amount of reducing agent, such as hydroxylamine. Brandt and Wise (*Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 1392) also report that in the estimation of vanadium with benzohydroxamic acid, all the vanadium must be present in the quinquevalent state. These facts suggest that the coloured products of vanadium are derivatives of pentavalent vanadium. Job's method of continued variation shows both the dull purple and bright purple colours formed in aqueous medium correspond to 1:3 complexes. In 50% alcohol also, Job's variation indicates 1:3 complexes in acid as well as in alkaline medium. All the coloured products are weak complexes as is evident from the fact that a very large excess of the reagent (about 60-70 times the molar proportion of vanadium in 50% alcoholic medium) is necessary for complete colour formation. Das Gupta and Singh (*loc. cit.*) report an 1:1 complex for vanadium benzohydroxamic acid in 50% alcohol at p_H 3.0. Bhaduri and Rây (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, **154**, 103) report an 1:1 complex for the blue colour produced by vanadium and salicylhydroxamic acid in aqueous medium

at p_H 3.0 to 3.8. They have also isolated a blue-black powder, having vanadium and the reagent in the ratio of 1:2, by working in a concentrated solution at about the same p_H . In the present case, all the soluble coloured products have been identified to have the same metal-reagent ratio. The acidic complex is extractable with higher alcohols whereas the coloured complex in alkaline range is non-extractable with organic solvents. Besides these coloured soluble products, a brownish black compound, having the metal-nicotinohydroxamic acid ratio as 1:1, has also been isolated by working in a concentrated solution at p_H about 3. This compound will be reported later.

Molybdenum (added as molybdate) develops with the reagent, an intense yellow colour which has been made the basis of colorimetric estimation of molybdenum over the p_H range 6.5 to 8. The colour has no absorption maximum in the visible region (sensitivity 0.026 γ at 380m μ and 0.032 γ at 390 m μ). Job's method indicates an 1:2 complex at this p_H range. Bhaduri and Rây (*loc. cit.*) report an 1:2 complex for the yellow colour formed between molybdenum and salicylhydroxamic acid at p_H 6.3 to 7. They have also isolated a yellow compound having molybdenum and the reagent in the ratio of 1:2 at p_H 3. Under suitable conditions, it has also been possible to obtain a yellow compound, which has the metal-nicotinohydroxamic acid ratio as 1:1. This compound will be reported in a subsequent communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fe^{III} solution was prepared from ferric nitrate; its iron content was determined gravimetrically as oxide. Fe^{II} solution was prepared by weighing G. R. ferrous ammonium sulphate. Vanadium solution was prepared from Analar ammonium vanadate. Vanadium content was estimated gravimetrically as vanadium pentoxide. Molybdenum solution was prepared by weighing pure MoO₃, dissolving in alkali, neutralising and finally making up to a known volume. All the standard solutions were appropriately diluted.

Preparation of nicotinohydroxamic acid hydrochloride has been described earlier (Dutta, *loc. cit.*). 1% Reagent solution was used.

A Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of optical density in 1 cm cells, unless otherwise mentioned. A Cambridge p_H -meter was used for the measurement of p_H .

In Figs. 1-3, the absorption spectra of iron (ferric and ferrous), vanadium (in aqueous as also in 50% ethanol medium) at different p_H values as well as that of molybdenum in presence of a large excess of the reagent are shown.

The golden yellow colour developed by iron was made use of for the colorimetric estimation of ferric or ferrous iron at p_H 4.5 to 6, optical density remaining constant over this p_H range. Colour intensity was measured at 440 m μ . For

FIG. 1
Absorption spectra.

- A. Fe^{3+} -nicotino-hydroxamate
(8 γ Fe/c.c.) at p_{H} 5.4.
B. Do at p_{H} 3.0 $\bar{c}$.
C. Do at p_{H} 1.8.
D. Fe^{3+} -nicotino-hydroxamate
(8 γ Fe/c.c.) at p_{H} 5.2.

FIG. 2
Absorption spectra.

- A. Vanadium-nicotino-hydroxamate
(8 γ V/c.c.), in 50% ethanol at p_{H} 3.76.
B. Do at p_{H} 8.92.
C. Vanadium (8 γ /c.c.)-nicotino-hydroxamate
in aq. medium at p_{H} 2.9.
D. Do at p_{H} 8.0.
E. Amyl alcohol extract of aq. vanadium nicotino-
hydroxamate colour (p_{H} of the aqueous
medium 3.06) (4 γ V/c.c.).

complete colour formation, an excess of the reagent, about 15-20 times the molar proportion of iron, is necessary. The colour is stable for about a day and then

fades slowly. Beer's law is obeyed by both ferrous and ferric iron over the range 0.5 to 8 γ iron (Fig. 4, curve 1). Sandell sensitivity is the same for both (0.014 γ). The effect of diverse ions on the colour intensity has been fully investigated with respect to 4 γ Fe/c.c. in a total volume of 25 c.c. (at p_{H} 4.5-5). Sulphate, chloride, nitrate, carbonate, borate, phosphate (150 γ), tartrate (50 γ), aluminium (40 γ), zinc, cadmium, lead, tungstate, manganese, copper (100 γ), nickel (150 γ), cobalt (100 γ), chromium (80 γ) do not interfere. In presence of titanium (60 γ), uranium (100 γ) and molybdenum (100 γ), the colour intensity should be measured at 500-520 μ , where absorption of the other coloured species is negligible. But serious interference is caused by citrate, oxalate and vanadium.

FIG. 3

- A. Job's curve of Mo-nicotino-hydroxamate
 p_{H} 7.0, 400 μ .
B. Do at 420 μ .
C. Spectra of molybdenum (20 γ /c.c.)
nicotino-hydroxamate, p_{H} 6.94.

The golden yellow colour developed by vanadium in 50% ethyl alcohol is highly sensitive and is suitable for the colorimetric estimation of the metal. Optical density of the colour remains constant over the wide range of p_H 2.5 to 4.5. The colour is perfectly stable. Beer's law is closely followed over the range 0.5 γ to 10 γ vanadium (Fig. 4, curve I). The optimum p_H for extraction of the aqueous colour is 3 to 4. The partition coefficient of the coloured product between water and the alcohol is not, however, highly favourable. Thus, it was felt necessary to extract the colour produced by 0.1 mg. vanadium at least three or four times by 5 c.c. portions of isobutyl alcohol and then making the volume to 25 c.c.

FIG. 4
Beer's law curves.

I, $\odot$ Fe^{3+} -nicotinohydroxamate colour at p_H 5.0, 440 $m\mu$.

V^{5+} " " at p_H 3.0 " (50% ethanol medium)

II. Mo^{6+} Nicotinohydroxamate colour at p_H 7.2, 390 $m\mu$.

Sandell sensitivity, in 50% ethyl alcohol at 440 $m\mu$, the optimum wave-length of measurement of the optical density, is 0.0147 and that by extraction procedure is 0.0127 at 440 $m\mu$. A large excess of the reagent (at least 60-70 times the molar proportion of vanadium) is necessary for complete colour formation. The effect of diverse ions on the colour intensity has been fully studied with respect to 4 γ V/c.c. in a total volume of 25 c.c. Ions such as nitrate, chloride, sulphate, borate, phosphate, acetate, thiocyanate, aluminium, cadmium, copper (80 γ), nickel (100 γ), cobalt (100 γ), lead, zinc, chromium (80 γ), manganese (120 γ), mercury, thorium do not interfere. In presence of molybdenum (100 γ) and uranium (50 γ), the colour should be measured at 500-520 $m\mu$. Citrate and iron interfere seriously. However, interference due to uranium and molybdenum can be eliminated by extraction procedure, but iron interferes as the iron hydroxamate complex is also partially extractable with higher alcohols.

The optical density of the molybdenum nicotinohydroxamate colour remains constant over the p_H range 6.8 to 8. Optimum wave-lengths for measurement of optical density is 380 $m\mu$ or 390 $m\mu$. The reagent solutions have slight absorption at these wave-lengths. Measurements should therefore be made against reagent blanks. A large excess of the reagent, at least 80 times the molar proportion of molybdenum, is required for maximum colour formation. Beer's law is perfectly obeyed over the range 2 to 20 γ Mo (Fig. 4, curve II). Many metal ions and anions interfere, either due to strong absorption at that wave-length or due to precipitation of the metal hydroxides.

Determination of Empirical Composition of the Coloured Complexes by Job's Method

A. Iron Complexes.—For the violet ferric complex, 0.001M solutions of ferric nitrate and 0.001M nicotinohydroxamic acid hydrochloride solutions were mixed.

(metal soln. + reagent soln. = 40 c.c.), p_H adjusted to 2, volume made up to 50 c.c. and the optical densities were then measured at 500 $m\mu$ and also at 550 $m\mu$ in a 2 cm cell. Optical density plot against mole fraction of the reagent shows a maximum at 0.5, indicating an 1:1 complex between ferric iron and the reagent (curve A, Fig. 5). For the red ferric complex, a similar determination was made at p_H 3.01 and optical densities read at 470 $m\mu$ and at 500 $m\mu$. Corrections for the colour developed by iron alone under similar conditions were made. Corrected optical densities (at 470 $m\mu$) were plotted against mole fraction of the reagent (curve A', Fig. 5). An 1:2 complex is thereby shown to exist.

FIG. 5.
Job's curves of iron nicotinohydroxamate.

- A. Fe^{3+} -Reagent, p_H 2, 500 $m\mu$.
 A'. Do p_H 3.01, 470 $m\mu$.
 B. Do p_H 5.3, 440 $m\mu$.
 C. Fe^{2+} -Reagent, p_H 5.30, 440 $m\mu$.

In another set 0.002 M ferric iron and 0.002 M reagent solutions were mixed (metal + reagent = 20 c.c.). To each of these solutions was added 20 c.c. of a sodium acetate-HCl buffer of p_H 5.3, the solutions made up to 50 c.c. and optical densities were read at 440 $m\mu$ and also at 500 $m\mu$ in 2 cm. cells. At 440 $m\mu$ the iron solutions at p_H 5.3 had some absorption, but only very negligible absorption at 500 $m\mu$. The absorption of iron under these conditions was determined separately and corrections for these absorptions made. The corrected optical densities were plotted against mole fraction of the reagent. The curves at 440 $m\mu$ and also at 500 $m\mu$ (not shown in Fig. 5) show a maximum at 0.75, indicating an 1:3 complex between ferric iron and the reagent (curve B, Fig. 5).

A similar determination was also made with 0.002 M ferrous ammonium sulphate and 0.002 M reagent solution at p_H 5.3. Here, however, in presence of acetate buffer the colour development was slow, and therefore the optical density measurements were taken after 2½ hours at 440 $m\mu$ and also at 500 $m\mu$ in 2 cm

cells. The ferrous solutions under these conditions had negligible absorption. Maximum in the optical density-mole fraction curve again occurs at 0.75, indicating an 1:3 complex (curve C, Fig. 5).

Fig. 6

Job's curves of vanadium nicotino-hydroxamate.

- A. 1:1 Alcoholic vanadium and 1:1 alcoholic reagent, p_H 3.0, 440 $m\mu$.
 B. Do p_H 8.5, 500 $m\mu$.
 C. Aqueous vanadium and aqueous reagent, p_H 8.0, 500 $m\mu$.
 D. Do p_H 3.0, 500 $m\mu$.

B. Vanadium Colours.—Aqueous equimolar (0.005 *M*) solutions of vanadate and reagent were mixed (metal + reagent = 40 c.c.), p_H adjusted to 3.0, the volume finally made up to 50 c.c. and the optical densities were read at 500 $m\mu$ and also at 550 $m\mu$ in 2 cm cells. Optical density-mole fraction curve shows an 1:3 complex. A similar measurement at p_H 8 gave the maximum in the Job's curve at 0.75, indicating the formation of an 1:3 complex (curves C and D, Fig. 6).

1:1 Alcoholic vanadium solutions (0.0025 *M*) and 1:1 alcoholic reagent solutions (0.0025 *M*) were mixed, keeping the total volume at 40 c.c.; p_H was adjusted to 3 and the volume finally made up to 50 c.c. and optical densities measured at 440 $m\mu$ and also at 500 $m\mu$. At 440 $m\mu$, correction for absorption of vanadium was made. Job's curve shows the maximum at 1:3 ratio. A similar measurement at p_H 8 with 0.005 *M* solutions at 500 $m\mu$ and at 550 $m\mu$ indicates an 1:3 complex (curves A and B, Fig. 6).

C. *Molybdenum Colours*.—Molybdenum solution (0.005M) and the reagent solution (0.005 M) were mixed, keeping the total volume at 40 c.c. p_H was adjusted to 7, volume made up to 50 c.c. and then optical densities measured in 1 cm cells at 400 m μ and at 420 m μ . Job's curves show a peak at 0.67, indicating an 1:2 complex (curves A & B, Fig. 3). The molybdenum solutions under the same conditions showed negligible absorption at 400 m μ and at 420 m μ .

D I S C U S S I O N

The hydroxamic acids generally exist in two tautomeric forms:

(I) has one replaceable hydrogen so that it would behave as a monobasic acid. The carbonyl oxygen may function as the co-ordinating source. On the other hand, structure (II) has two replaceable hydrogens, one, of the hydroxyl group and the other, of the oxime group, so that the hydroxamic acid might behave as a dibasic acid. Experiments with pyridinohydroxamic acids have revealed a close similarity in their reaction towards metal ions. Nicotino and isonicotino-hydroxamic acids give rise to the intensely coloured manganic complexes in ammoniacal medium. The nature of iron complexes of these reagents is essentially the same. In their behaviour towards vanadium they reveal a slight difference in that the addition of alcohol to the brown-purple vanadium isonicotinohydroxamate in acid medium, does not produce that intense golden yellow colour as developed with nicotinohydroxamic acid in 50% alcoholic medium. Instead, a dirty brown-yellow colour (with no absorption maximum in the visible) is formed.

Their reaction towards molybdenum is also similar. Picolinohydroxamic acid gives only a weakly coloured manganic complex, develops the usual violet ferric complex and in weak-acid solution gives a precipitate. This reagent exhibits the intense golden yellow vanadium colour in presence of alcohol in acid medium. Its behaviour towards molybdenum is also similar to those of nicotino- and isonicotino-hydroxamic acids.

These similarities suggest that the reactions shown by these reagents are probably entirely those of the hydroxamic acid groups and possibly the heterocyclic nitrogen does merely influence the solubilities of the metal complexes.

The nature and the analytical aspects of the colour reactions of iron (ferric and ferrous), vanadium and molybdenum with picolino- and isonicotino-hydroxamic acids will form the subject matter of a subsequent communication.

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